

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN OUR LIFE

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In the modern world, learning a foreign language is one of the most important parts of being a successful modern person. Knowing at least one foreign language will broaden your horizons and allow you to experience the culture and customs of another nation. Today, millions of people are learning foreign languages all over the world. English plays an important role in our life. It is necessary for people of all ages. English is associated with all walks of life. It is indispensable for anyone who wants to get prestigious training or find a well-paid job. From the data presented in our article, it can be concluded that employees who know English are paid more than those who don't. This fact can be a great incentive to learn foreign vocabulary and grammar.

Many people around the world study foreign languages: French, German, Spanish, English, Italian and others. But the most popular is of course English. Why is that? I think there are several reasons for its popularity. First, children learn this in school. They study it in universities and institutes because it is easier to learn than other languages. Secondly, it sounds very nice and pleasant. Third, English is used in global media. This language is necessary when we travel abroad because we need to communicate with people of different nationalities. English is an international language spoken in more than 120 countries, making it the working language of the United Nations. Also, many people want to use it for their future career. English is now a language of communication for professionals all over the world. English attracts us because it is used everywhere and you find it everywhere: on the labels of different products, on various notices. Today, there are many borrowings from Russian into English. And we cannot understand the meaning of these words without knowing the language. Every modern person should try to learn English. There are so many English books at every step that they are worth reading in their original form. Also, many songs, films and other cultural material are written in English and if we do our best we will understand them without translation. With our connections, people around the world have grown exponentially. There is now a practice of exchanging specialists in different areas of life. This is another reason to learn English. The role of language in public life.

Practice shows that in the most profitable position in the labor market, in addition to mastering the main profession, there are professionals who know

one or more foreign languages: to keep up to date with the latest news from the world of science and technology. You must be able to read the articles in their original language. Moreover, it is much easier to work with foreign partners when you have the basic knowledge. Learning English gives us the freedom to communicate in the modern world. English is a global language and should be learned quickly as we live in the modern world.

Language is a means of communication. Performing a communicative function, the ability to convey information, messages about objects serves as a means of communication and thought. The tongue is a sensory organ that allows you to speak and hear. Language is a part of our body and it doesn't get any more complicated than that. Language is a part of our body and no less than the organism itself. The role of foreign languages is increasing. Today, there are approximately 3,000 languages in the world, of which English is the most widely spoken. It is the official language of many countries: United States, Great Britain, Northern Ireland, Australia, New Zealand. It is one of the official languages

of Canada, Ireland and the Republic of South Africa. It is the second language of India and South Africa.

Thanks to our knowledge of English, we can read books and magazines in their originals, talk to foreigners, translate articles, and achieve success in sports. In addition, joint ventures developing in our country need specialists with in-depth knowledge of English. Knowledge of English is an absolute must for any trained and good quality professional. Our country is transitioning to a market economy. This is why learning English and other languages is so important.

The spread of English around the world began with its early travels to the Americas and Asia and continued with the colonial conquest of Africa and the South. Pacific in the 19th century. A crucial step was taken in the 20th century when newly formed countries adopted English as one of the official or official languages. English is not just a science taught in the classroom. It is used in real situations. A foreign language is absolutely necessary for any educated person, modern professional... It all depends on our conditions. Let's not forget the rules of language learning: "Learn to speak! Learn to read by reading. . Nowadays, people are often confronted with the fact that mastering a foreign language becomes a vital necessity. It should be noted that the most popular language at the moment is English. A foreign language contributes to the development of thought processes. This is because when learning a foreign language you have to work with a different character system. Language teaches us to think logically and choose the right option among the different meanings of each word. From

all the above, we can conclude that the need for English is increasing every year. English is taking a big step in our lives. You need to learn English to keep track of time. It should also be noted that learning is never too late.

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